

STATE BUDGET OF RESOURCE TAXES KEEPING ITS INCOME IN FORMATION PLACE AND SIGNIFICANCE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11109294>

Annotation. Ensuring the free activity of business entities, radically reducing their interference in the activities of state bodies, early prevention of violations, and preventive measures to increase the efficiency of the state in the field of economic development are important priority tasks of the internal affairs bodies.

Keywords Tax, financial policy, market economy, account interests, the main purpose of the tax.

Introduction.

Ensuring the free activity of business entities, they State to the activity organs intervention fundamentally shorten, early prevention of violations, preventive measures increasing efficiency of the state in the field of economic development is an important priority task of the polic.

Rational formation of state tax policy and system in the country development of entrepreneurship and attraction of foreign investments provides the creation of favorable conditions. ¹

Taxes fill the state treasury in conditions of market relations since they are considered the main source, they are responsible for solving the most important tasks of the state, forming the income part of the state budget to consider the necessary amount of funds as a lever for gathering it is necessary.

Tax is a financial policy aimed at a specific goal together they redistribute a part of the gross national product and thus the structure of the economy directly participates in changing its structure and ensuring the guarantee of social protection of the population. Tax relationship of participants economic taking into account their interests and their mutual interests provision is the correct organization of these relations. Parties and to ensure common interests, it is classical and universal it will be necessary to follow the principles of taxation.

¹ T. Malikov in his monograph entitled "Budget-Tax Policy", financial, budget among senior scholars and "as a synonym" if the sentences like tax policy are derived from the content of the text their opinions about whether its use is considered "understandable" or "incorrect" for these scientists said and won. We also want to understand these concepts from the essence of the text.

Classical and universally recognized taxation of taxation compliance with the principles of optimizing the rate of tax burden, tax increasing the interest of the payer in the development of production, investments and to modernization funds to be directed leads to stimulation.

In the first years of independence, the main goal of tax policy was mainly to ensure state interests, that is, the state budget if it is aimed at collecting more funds, in the following years its goal will be based on the principle of "strong state-strong civil society" legality provide and the economy development is focused on stimulation.

The budget and tax policy of any country is to collect funds for the treasury along with economic sectors service to development it is necessary to ensure that. That is why the state budget in our country activities of business entities in the development of tax policy special attention is paid to support issues.

In the years of independence, the basis of the market economy in our country stable legislation that strengthens the priority of private property it is necessary to note that the database has been created. On the rapid development of small business and private entrepreneurship, which is an important factor in the formation of the class of middle owners, the sustainable development of the country's economy, the creation of new jobs and the increase of the population's income favorable business environment and reliable legal guarantees have been created. A favorable business environment and reliable legal guarantees have been created for the rapid development of small business and private entrepreneurship, which is an important factor for the formation of the middle class of owners, the stable development of the country's economy, the creation of new jobs and the increase of the population's income.

Japanese scientist Lee Dj of public spending and economic growth The structure of public expenditure and its optimality based on the Barro model the total amount of budget expenses as a result of studying the amount economic growth in cases where income tax is limited and high decrease, on the contrary, the income tax is relatively low and the state economic growth is high in cases where expenses are directed to investment came to the conclusion that it will be.

This practice is an acceptable level of public spending for public investment in the case of East Asian countries direction to ensure high economic growth today, we are all witnesses to the fact that it has proven itself.

In the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, it is not for nothing that the continuation of a reasonable tax policy to optimize the tax burden is not set as one of the main goals.

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